
APPENDIX OF MODAL FUNCTIONAL (“DIALECTICA”) INTERPRETATION

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ABSTRACT. We adapt our light Dialectica interpretation to usual and light modal formulas (with universal quantification on boolean and natural variables) and prove it sound for a non-standard modal arithmetic based on Gödel’s T and classical S_4 . The range of this *light modal Dialectica* is the usual (non-modal) classical Arithmetic in all finite types (with booleans); the propositional kernel of its domain is Boolean and not S_4 . The ‘heavy’ modal Dialectica interpretation is a new technique, as it cannot be simulated within our previous light Dialectica. The synthesized functionals are at least as good as before, while the translation process is improved. Through our modal Dialectica, the existence of a realizer for the defining axiom of classical S_5 reduces to the Drinking Principle (cf. Smullyan).

Our Minlog variant and implementation of modal Dialectica may be found at <https://triffon.github.io/mlfd>. Paper main body at arXiv:1212.0020.

APPENDIX A. MINLOG CODE FOR UNBOUNDED PIGEONHOLE PRINCIPLE TERM SYNTHESIS

;; Unbounded (Infinite) Pigeonhole Principle, adapted by Hernest from Trifonov’s 2009
;; incomplete solution. We here follow the methodic approach exposed in Trifonov’s thesis,
;; but with the optimization brought by modal Dialectica (via impnc), rather than allnc

```
(load "C:\\minlog\\initDan.scm") ;; init for Windows pathnames
(load "C:\\minlog\\etsmdA.scm") ;; modal Dialectica extraction module
(set! COMENTARIU #f) (set! COMMENT-FLAG #f)
(libload "nat.scm"); symbols ‘m’, ‘n’, ‘k’ of type nat and rudimentary numbers operations
(libload "list.scm"); elementary operations on lists algebra, mainly over numbers algebra
(add-var-name "k" (py "nat")) ;; number of colors
(add-var-name "b" (py "nat")) ;; symbol for a variable color between 0 and k-1
(add-var-name "f" (py "nat=>nat")) ;; symbol for tapes, i.e., infinite sequences of colors
(add-var-name "ll" (py "list nat")) ;; variable symbol for lists of natural numbers
;; ‘Finite Colouring’ : tape f is constrained to feature only colors 0,...,(k-1)
(define FC ;; ‘there are at most k colors on the tape f’, free variables ‘k’ and ‘f’
  (pf " all n. f n < k ")) below ‘F’ is Minlog’s decidable falsum atom(ff), boolean ‘ff’
(define notFC (pf " (all n. f n < k) -> F ")) ;; negation of ‘FC’, free vars ‘k’ and ‘f’
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Key words and phrases: Kreisel implication, extractive Proof Theory, quantified modal logic, automatic program synthesis, code-carrying classical proofs, Proof Mining .

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;; 'Infinite Colouring with b': the color b occurs infinitely often on tape f
(define INFCb ;; bound variable 'm' here is essentially computational under Dialectica
  (pf "all n. all m (n <= m -> f m = b -> F) -> F")) ;; free variables 'b' and 'f'
(define notINFC ;; universally closed for 'b' negation of 'INFCb', with 'f' still free
  (pf "all b. (all n. all m (n <= m -> f m = b -> F) -> F) -> F"))
; Infinite Pigeonhole Principle, here negatively expressed for a proof by contradiction
(define IPH (make-all (pv "f") (make-imp notINFC notFC))) ; if tape f has no infinite
; monochromatic subsequence, then it is not finitely coloured; free var 'k' in notFC only
;; there is a list ll of length n+1 containing different indices of occurrence
;; of the same color
(define STLZ (pf "(all ll . Lh ll = Succ n ->
  (all m . m < n -> (Succ m thof ll) < (m thof ll)) -->
  (all m . m < n -> f(m thof ll) = f(Succ m thof ll)) --> F) -> F ")
;; the free variables are 'f' and 'n', 'm' needs not be realized
(define notSTLZ (pf "all ll . Lh ll = Succ n ->
  (all m . m < n -> (Succ m thof ll) < (m thof ll)) -->
  (all m . m < n -> f(m thof ll) = f(Succ m thof ll)) --> F ") ; Kreisel implication(s)
; finite monochromatic subsequences of arbitrary length weakly exist
;; for color b and tape f
(define STLZb (pf "all n. (all ll . Lh ll = Succ n ->
  (all m . m < n -> (Succ m thof ll) < (m thof ll)) -->
  (all m . m < Succ n -> f(m thof ll) = b) --> F) -> F ")
(define Goal (mk-imp INFCb STLZb)) ;; free variables 'b' and 'f' to be universally closed
(define FinalGoal (mk-all (pv "k") (pv "n") (pv "f") (mk-imp notSTLZ notFC)))

(add-rewrite-rule (pt "NegConst (NegConst boole^)") (pt "boole^")) ;; Boolean Stability
(add-rewrite-rule (pt "ImpConst boole^ False") (pt "NegConst boole^")) ;; simplification

(set-goal IPH)
(ind) ; induction on the number of colors 'k'
(strip) ; minimal logic proof (search) wrongly produces a proof with free variable 'n'
(use 2 (pt "0")) ; this is a manual bug-fix for (modal) Dialectica program extraction
; simple base case, now to the step case
(assume "k" "IH" "f" "NotINFC" "FCSucck")
(use "NotINFC" (pt "k"))
(assume "n" "nIsLastForK")
;; IH is: all f (all b exca n all m (n<=m -> f m=b -> F) -> all n f n<k -> F)
(use "IH" (pt "[n1]f(n max n1)")) ; var f is instantiated with (lambda n1. f(n max n1))
(ng) ;----- normalize the current goal
(assume "b" "u") ;; assumption u is: all n0 exca m (n0<=m ! f(n max m)=b), '! is &ca
(use "NotINFC" (pt "b"))
(assume "n1" "u1") ;; assumption u1 is: all m (n1<=m -> f m=b -> F)
(use "u" (pt "n1"))
(assume "m" "n1<=m" "f(n max m)=b")
(use "u1" (pt "n max m"))
(use "NatLeTrans" (pt "m")); all nat1,nat2,nat3(nat1<=nat2 -> nat2<=nat3 -> nat1<=nat3)
(use "n1<=m")
(use "NatMaxUB2") ;; all nat1,nat2 (nat2 <= (nat1 max nat2))
(use "f(n max m)=b")
(ng) ;----- normalize the current goal
(assume "n1")
;"all nat1,nat2 (nat1<Succ nat2 -> (nat1<nat2 -> Pvar) -> (nat1=nat2 -> Pvar) -> Pvar)"
(use "NatLtSuccCases" (pt "f(n max n1)")) (pt "k"))
(use "FCSucck") ;; all n (f n < Succ k)
(search) ;; quick automated proof-search in minimal quantifier logic

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(assume "f(n max n1)=k")
(use "Efq") ;; Ex Falso Quodlibet is a 'global assumption' simulating 'F -> Pvar'
(use "nIsLastForK" (pt "n max n1")) ; all m (n<=m -> f m=k -> F)
(use "NatMaxUB1"          ) ; ; all nat1,nat2 (nat1 <= nat1 max nat2)
(use "f(n max n1)=k")
(save "IPH")
;----- proof of Infinite Pigeonhole finished and saved

(set! COMMENT-FLAG #t)
(set! ETSMD-LET-ENABLED #t)
(define extr_term-iph
  (proof-to-extracted-md-term
    (nbe-normalize-proof (expand-theorems (theorem-name-to-proof "IPH")))))
(define nterm-iph (nbe-normalize-term extr_term-iph))
; (pretty-print nterm-iph) ; 115 lines - functional for Infinite Pigeonhole principle

(add-program-constant "mdIPH" (term-to-type nterm-iph))
(define (animate-iph)
  (add-computation-rule "mdIPH k f"
    (nbe-normalize-term (mk-term-in-app-form nterm-iph (pt "k") (pt "f")))))
(define (deanimate-iph)
  (remove-computation-rules-for (pt "mdIPH k f")))
(set! COMMENT-FLAG #f)

(set-goal Goal) ; if color b appears infinitely often on tape f then it occurs
; finitely often, i.e., for any n there (weakly) exists a list l of length n+1 of
; indices l_0,..,l_n pointing to b-coloured cells of f, i.e., f(l_m)=b, m in [0..n]
(assume "f" "b" "Infb") ;; Infb is: all n exca m (n<=m ! f m=b)
(ind) ; base case of induction on n, i.e., list length minus one
(assume "NotSTLZero") ;; NotSTLb with b replaced by zero, i.e., (pt "0")
(use "Infb" (pt "0"))
(assume "m" "0<=m" "f m=b")
(use "NotSTLZero" (pt "m:"))
(use "Truth-Axiom")
(normalize-goal)
(assume "m1")
(use "Efq") ;----- first use of 'boolean' Ex Falso
(cases) ;; proof by case distinction, here for numbers algebra, hence 0 vs. > 0
(strip) ;; give up the dummy premise in '?_13: 0<1 -> f(0 thof m:)=b'
(use "f m=b") ;; since the zero-th element of the singleton list 'm:' is 'm'
(normalize-goal)
(assume "m1")
(use "Efq") ;; finished base case of 'n'-induction, now proceed to step case
(assume "n" "IH" "NotSTLZ")
(use "IH")
(cases) ;; proof by case distinction, here for lists algebra, hence nil vs. non-nil
(normalize-goal)
(use "Efq") ;----- third use of 'boolean' Ex Falso
(assume "m" "l1")
(assume "Lh l1=n") ;; length of list l1 is n
(assume "l1IsDecreasing") ;; indexes from 'l1' are (strictly) decreasing, hence different
(assume "l1IsMonochrome") ;; indexes from list l point to a monochromatic subsequence
(use "Infb" (pt "Succ m"))
(assume "m1" "m<m1" "f m1=b")
(use "NotSTLZ" (pt "m1::m:l1")); NotSTLZ for (cons m1 (cons m l1)), a list of length n+2

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(use "Lh l1=n")
(cases) ;; proof by numbers case distinction
(assume "0 < Succ n") ;; discard dummy premise
(use "NatSuccLeToLt") ;; all nat1,nat2 ((Succ nat1) <= nat2 -> nat1 < nat2)
(use "m<m1")
(use "l1IsDecreasing")
(cases) ;; proof by numbers case distinction
(assume "0 < Succ(Succ n)") ;; discard dummy premise
(use "f m1=b")
(use "l1IsMonochrome")
(save "Goal")
;----- intermediate Goal proof completed and saved
(set! COMMENT-FLAG #t)
(set! ETSMD-LET-ENABLED #t)
(define extr_term-g (proof-to-extracted-md-term
  (nbe-normalize-proof (expand-theorems (theorem-name-to-proof "Goal")))))
(add-program-constant "mdGoal" (term-to-type extr_term-g))
; (pretty-print extr_term-g) ; 38 lines
; (define nterm-g (nbe-normalize-term extr_term-g))
; (pretty-print nterm-g) ; 13 lines
(define (animate-goal) (add-computation-rule "mdGoal f k"
  (nbe-normalize-term (mk-term-in-app-form extr_term-g (pt "f") (pt "k")))))
(define (deanimate-goal)
  (remove-computation-rules-for (pt "mdGoal f k")))
(set! COMMENT-FLAG #f)

(set-goal FinalGoal); no monochromatic subsequence of length n+1, then >k colors on f
(assume "k" "n" "f" "NotSTLZ" "FC")
(use "IPH" (pt "k") (pt "f")); use lemma IPH with given arguments from actual context
(assume "b" "Infb")
(use "Goal" (pt "f") (pt "b") (pt "n")); use Goal with arguments from updated context
(use "Infb")
(assume "l" "Lh l=Succ n" "l1IsDecreasing" "l1IsMonochrome")
(use "NotSTLZ" (pt "l"))
(use "Lh l=Succ n")
(use "l1IsDecreasing")
(assume "m" "m<n")
(use "NatEqTrans" (pt "b")); all nat1,nat2,nat3 (nat1=nat2 -> nat2=nat3 -> nat1=nat3)
(use "l1IsMonochrome")
;- use transitivity of '<' ; all nat1,nat2,nat3 (nat1<nat2 -> nat2<nat3 -> nat1<nat3)
(use "NatLtTrans" (pt "Succ m")) ;; nat1 := Succ m; automatic bindings for nat2, nat3
(use "Truth-Axiom")
(use "m<n")
(use "NatEqSym"); symmetry of '=' for numbers: all nat1,nat2 (nat1=nat2 -> nat2=nat1)
(use "l1IsMonochrome")
(use "m<n")
(use "FC")
(save "FinalGoal")

(set! COMMENT-FLAG #t)
(set! ETSMD-LET-ENABLED #t)
(define extr_term-km
  (proof-to-extracted-md-term (theorem-name-to-proof "FinalGoal")))
(nldisplay (type-to-string (term-to-type extr_term-km)))
; (pretty-print extr_term-km) ; 5 lines

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;=====
; Trifon's TEST and Dan's Random
;=====

; generate a list of 2^n infinite sequences starting with all possible variations
; of n booleans and continuing with #f, i.e., 0 (also 1 is used for #t)
(define (generate-seq n)
  (if (= n 0)
      (list (lambda (n) 0))
      (foldr (lambda (x l)
              (cons (lambda (n) (if (= n 0) 0 (x (- n 1))))
                    (cons (lambda (n) (if (= n 0) 1 (x (- n 1))))
                          1)))) '() (generate-seq (- n 1))))))

; generate one sequence of colors 0 .. (k-1) with initial k^n
; elements randomly generated and continuing with color 0
(define (grand-itm k) (if (and (fxpositive? k) (> k 1))
  (rand-itm k) (myerror "grand-itm: not exact positive arg or k=1")))
(define (rand-itm k) (fxmodulo (random (most-positive-fixnum)) k))
(define (grand-seq k n) (if (and (fxpositive? k) (> k 1) (fxpositive? n))
  (rand-seq k (expt k n))
  (myerror "grand-seq: not exact positive args or k=1")))
(define (rand-seq k e) (first (lambda (m) (rand-itm k)) e))
(define (seq-fn seq) (let* ((fxv (list->fxvector seq))
  (len (fxvector-length fxv))
  (lambda (m) (if (< m len)
    (fxvector-ref fxv m) 0))))))

; return a list of (f 0), (f 1), ..., (f n-1)
(define (first f n)
  (if (= n 0) '() (cons (f 0) (first (lambda (n) (f (+ n 1))) (- n 1)))))

; test a Scheme program on a list of infinite binary sequences
(define (test-bseq program . l)
  (let ((len (if (null? l) 4 (car l))))
    (map (lambda (seq)
          (display "Testing on: ") (display (first seq len))
          (let ((p (program seq))) (cmdisplay "Result:"
            (car p) "." (cdr p))))
         (generate-seq len)))
  *the-non-printing-object*)

; test the Scheme program on one infinite sequence of random colors
(define (test-rseq p k n l)
  (let* ((len (fxmax 4 l))
  (lseq (rand-seq k len))
  (fseq (seq-fn lseq))
  (res ((p k) n) fseq)))
  (display "Testing on: ") (display lseq)
  (cmdisplay "Result:"
  (car res) "." (cdr res)))

; definitions needed for term-to-scheme-expr

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(define (|ListAppend| l1)
  (lambda (l2)
    (append l1 l2)))

(define (|listrec| l)
  (lambda (base)
    (lambda (step)
      (if (null? l)
          base
          (((step (car l)) (cdr l))
           (((|listrec| (cdr l)) base) step))))))

(define (|NatMax| n1)
  (lambda (n2)
    (max n1 n2)))

(define |ListLength| length)

(define (|ListProj| n)
  (lambda (l) (if (< n (length l)) (list-ref l n) 0)))

; prepare a Scheme program for modal Dialectica translation
(define (prepare-a term k n)
  (let ((prog (eval (term-to-scheme-expr term)))) ((prog k) n))

; animate subprograms for modular modal Dialectica
(define |mdGoal| (eval (term-to-scheme-expr extr_term-g)))
(define |mdIPH| (eval (term-to-scheme-expr nterm-iph)))

; Trifon's complete test, here for modular modal Dialectica translation
(test-bseq (prepare-a extr_term-km 2 1)) ; for 2-coloring require two indices l_0 , l_1
; output is correct and immediate - see the next Appendix section

; Scheme program for Unbounded Pigeonhole
(define prog (eval (term-to-scheme-expr extr_term-km)))

; Dan's test on a randomly generated sequence (each call is for yet another sequence)
(time (test-rseq prog 3 3 81)) ; only 81 = 3^4 first colors on tape need to be random
;; ; 33 minutes [worst case!] runtime for 3 colors and 4 indexes; output always in [0,80]
;; ; > Testing on:
;; ; (0 1 1 2 0 1 2 2 1 1 1 2 1 2 0 1 0 1 0 2 0 2 1 0 2 0 0 0 0 1 1 2 1 0 2 0 0 1 2 1
;; ; 0 0 0 0 0 2 1 1 0 2 2 0 1 2 2 1 1 1 1 2 2 1 0 1 2 2 0 0 2 1 0 2 0 0 1 2 1 0 2 0 1)
;; ; (Result: 41 . (44 43 42 41))
;; ; - the color is 0, the last 4 of the 5 zeros in the middle of the 81-length sequence
;; ; (time (test-rseq prog 3 3 81))
;; ; 114842 collections
;; ; 1940934 ms elapsed cpu time, including 21405 ms collecting
;; ; 1940874 ms elapsed real time, including 20796 ms collecting
;; ; 483706748128 bytes allocated, including 483704052400 bytes reclaimed

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APPENDIX B. NORMALIZED TERM FOR UNBOUNDED PIGEONHOLE PRINCIPLE

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; (pp extr_term-km); 5 lines; raw functional term extracted from 'FinalGoal'

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> [k,n,f]

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left(mdIPH k f)([b,f8508]right(mdGoal f b)f8508 n)@
left(mdGoal f left(right(mdIPH k f)([b,f8508]right(mdGoal f b)f8508 n)))
right(right(mdIPH k f)([b,f8508]right(mdGoal f b)f8508 n))
n

; (pp nterm-g); 13 lines; functional term 'mdGoal' extracted from 'Goal' proof

> [f0,n1]
([f2,n3]
  (Rec nat=>list nat)n3(f2 0):
  ([n4,15][if 15 (Nil nat) ([n6,17]f2(Succ n6)::n6::17]))@
([f2,n3]
  (Rec nat=>nat)n3 0
  ([n4,n5]
    [let n6
      [if ((Rec nat=>list nat)n4(f2 0):
          ([n6,17][if 17 (Nil nat) ([n8,19]f2(Succ n8)::n8::19))])
        0
        ([n6,17]Succ n6)]
      [if (negb(n6<=f2 n6 impb negb(f0(f2 n6)=n1))) n5 n6]]))

; (pp nterm-iph); 115 lines; functional term 'mdIPH' extracted from 'IPH' proof
;; (av "y" (py "nat@@(nat=>nat)"))
;; (av "x" (py "(nat=>(nat=>nat)=>nat)"))
;; (av "BiG" (py "(nat=>nat)=>((nat=>(nat=>nat)=>nat)=>nat)@@(
  (nat=>(nat=>nat)=>nat)=>nat@@(nat=>nat) )" ) )

> [n0]
(Rec nat=>(nat=>nat)=>((nat=>(nat=>nat)=>nat)=>nat)@@(
  (nat=>(nat=>nat)=>nat)=>nat@@(nat=>nat) ) )

n0
([f3]([x4]0)@([x4]0@([n5]0)))
([n3,BiG4,f5]
  ([x6]
    x6 n3
    ([n7]
      n7 max
      left(BiG4([n8]f5(n7 max n8)))([n8,f9]x6 n8([n10]n7 max f9 n10)))max
    left(BiG4
      ([n7]
        f5
        (x6 n3
          ([n8]
            n8 max
            left(BiG4([n9]f5(n8 max n9)))
            ([n9,f10]x6 n9([n11]n8 max f10 n11)))max
          n7)))
    ([n7,f8]
      x6 n7
      ([n9]
        x6 n3
        ([n10]
          n10 max
          left(BiG4([n11]f5(n10 max n11)))
          ([n11,f12]x6 n11([n13]n10 max f12 n13)))max
          f8 n9)))@

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```

([x6]
 [let y7
  (n3@
   ([n7]
    n7 max
    left(BiG4([n8]f5(n7 max n8)))([n8,f9]x6 n8([n10]n7 max f9 n10))))
 ([if (x6 left y7 right y7<=right y7(x6 left y7 right y7)impb
  negb(f5(right y7(x6 left y7 right y7))=left y7))
  (left(right(BiG4
   ([n8]
    f5
    (x6 n3
     ([n9]
      n9 max
      left(BiG4([n10]f5(n9 max n10)))
      ([n10,f11]x6 n10([n12]n9 max f11 n12)))max
      n8)))
   ([n8,f9]
    x6 n8
    ([n10]
     x6 n3
     ([n11]
      n11 max
      left(BiG4([n12]f5(n11 max n12)))
      ([n12,f13]x6 n12([n14]n11 max f13 n14)))max
      f9 n10))))
  (left y7)]@
 ([n8]
  [if (x6 left y7 right y7<=right y7(x6 left y7 right y7)impb
  negb(f5(right y7(x6 left y7 right y7))=left y7))
  (x6 n3
   ([n9]
    n9 max
    left(BiG4([n10]f5(n9 max n10)))
    ([n10,f11]x6 n10([n12]n9 max f11 n12)))max
    right(right(BiG4
     ([n9]
      f5
      (x6 n3
       ([n10]
        n10 max
        left(BiG4([n11]f5(n10 max n11)))
        ([n11,f12]x6 n11([n13]n10 max f12 n13)))max
        n9)))
     ([n9,f10]
      x6 n9
      ([n11]
       x6 n3
       ([n12]
        n12 max
        left(BiG4([n13]f5(n12 max n13)))
        ([n13,f14]x6 n13([n15]n12 max f14 n15)))max
        f10 n11)))
    n8)
  (right y7 n8)])))]))

```

